

The First European Expert Forum on Frontier AI

A summary of the first meeting on 23. April 2026, endorsed by 53 participants*

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Abstract

On 23 April 2026, the European Commission’s AI Office convened over 100 experts, from European AI developers, industry, investors, research, academia and think tanks, alongside Member States and Commission services, for the first meeting of the European Expert Forum on Frontier AI. The Forum aims to inform the European Frontier AI Initiative with recommendations to strengthen EU competitiveness, sovereignty and security in frontier AI. This paper synthesises over four hours of discussion across an opening plenary and six breakout sessions, organised by degree of consensus: points of notable convergence, points of partial convergence, and contested points that remain unresolved at this stage. In keeping with the Chatham House Rule, contributions are reported without attribution. Written independently of the Commission, this document aims to capture the main recurring points and to make them transparent to a broader public, without claiming to be exhaustive about everything that was said.

Executive Summary

On 23 April 2026, the European Commission’s AI Office convened over 100 experts, from European AI developers, industry, investors, research, academia and think tanks, alongside Member States and Commission services, for the first meeting of the European Expert Forum on Frontier AI. The Forum aims to inform the European Frontier AI Initiative with recommendations to strengthen EU competitiveness, sovereignty and security in frontier AI. This paper synthesises over four hours of discussion across six breakout sessions, organised by degree of consensus: points of notable convergence, points of partial convergence, and contested points that remain unresolved at this stage. Per the Chatham House Rule, contributions are unattributed.

Points of notable convergence

- AI capability progress is fast and accelerating, and current trajectories point to highly disruptive AI systems within a few years.
- The EU is far behind the US and China in frontier AI capabilities, compute infrastructure, and the wider ecosystem, and on the current trajectory the gap is widening rather than closing.

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- The main bottlenecks to EU AI competitiveness are access to capital, energy and data permitting delays, and specific regulatory obstacles, all preventing fast compute buildout. Issues with talent retention and attraction, as well as underperforming demand-side levers, are also part of the picture.
- Frontier AI developments directly affect EU national security and are not just a matter of economic competitiveness.
- EU sovereignty requires secure access to frontier AI systems and sufficient inference computing capacity to operate such systems at competitive scale.
- EU AI sovereignty does not require autarky, but leverage and interdependency.
- EU institutions and Member States need more internal AI expertise, directly advising the highest political level, and faster, more anticipatory processes that continuously leverage external expertise.
- European political leaders must prioritise action now and at a scale not yet contemplated. Without decisive action in the coming months, the European strategic position might become unrecoverable.

Points of partial convergence

- Europe should pursue a ‘middle power’ coalition with allied democracies to pool supply-chain leverage and capabilities development.
- Open-source / open-weight models are a strategic asset for European sovereignty, adoption and competition.
- Europe needs an ARPA-style moonshot funder for AI reliability, safety and security research, in the EUR 100m to 2bn/year range.
- Europe needs a verification, evaluation and safety capability, including for cryptographic proofs, audits and assurance, built on European soil.
- Physical AI / robotics / world models is the area of strongest convergence as a ‘next wave’ bet for Europe.
- Europe should support frontier-adjacent European companies as ‘fast followers’ even if they are not at the frontier.
- Europe has a real advantage in private and industrial data.

Contested / unresolved points

- Can Europe ‘leapfrog’ the current paradigm by betting on a new architecture (world models, energy efficiency, distributed AI, quantum) instead of chasing scale?
- Should Europe aim to build its own frontier models rather than accept being a fast follower or interdependent partner?
- Should general-purpose / scaled models or narrow / domain-specific AI be Europe’s primary bet?
- Is the framing of AI as primarily a danger (versus an opportunity) itself a strategic liability for Europe?
- Is the dominant US AI investment trajectory a sustainable trend or a bubble Europe should not chase?

1 Introduction

On the 23 April 2026, over 100 experts, spanning European AI developers, industry, investors, research, academia, think tanks, Member States and Commission services, were brought together

by the European Commission’s AI Office in the first meeting of the European Expert Forum on Frontier AI. The Expert Forum aims to inform the Frontier AI Initiative with recommendations on strategic actions to enhance competitiveness, sovereignty and security of the EU in frontier AI. The Frontier AI Initiative was announced in the European Commission’s Apply AI Strategy in October 2025. Strategic actions under the Frontier AI Initiative can contribute to building European frontier AI capabilities, or enhance Europe’s ability to access, choose, control, and benefit from any frontier AI model.

This paper synthesises over four hours of impulse statements and discussions, in the opening plenary as well as six different breakout sessions. The summary is organised by degree of consensus. It distinguishes points of notable convergence from points of partial convergence, i.e. proposals supported by some but not all, and from contested points, on which the experts were divided. In keeping with the Chatham House Rule, contributions are reported without attribution. This summary is based on extensive notes taken by multiple forum participants. These notes may be incomplete and transcription inaccuracies cannot be ruled out. This document was written without involvement of the European Commission and does not represent its views. Nor does it represent the views of the authors or the endorsers, who merely confirm that the summary corresponds to what they heard on the day.

The AI Office has announced that it would also publish key insights from the Forum, debrief relevant actors across the Commission and the Member States, and ensure that priority areas identified from the first meeting of the Expert Forum will feed into further expert exchanges, through written input, targeted workshops, or other dedicated exchanges. This summary can hopefully support these accountability efforts from the AI Office. Strategic actions taken under the Frontier AI Initiative will shape Europe’s position in one of the most consequential technological developments of our time. We publish this summary to make the substance of the Forum’s discussions accessible to a wider audience ahead of the forthcoming AI Office communications, offering an independent, granular account of the exchanges. Our aim is to give readers outside the room a clearer sense of where expert opinion currently stands, and so to support informed engagement with the Initiative and with frontier AI policy decisions more broadly, for the wider community of stakeholders, researchers, and members of the public with an interest in this field.

2 Points of notable convergence

2.1 AI capability progress is fast and accelerating, and current trajectories point to highly disruptive AI systems within a few years

- Frontier AI model performance has steadily improved across benchmarks. Within a few years, frontier AI systems have gone from struggling with basic math and coding tasks to being extremely proficient in these domains and in other reasoning tasks.
- A current frontier model reportedly solved an unsolved problem from a published frontier-math suite, considered publishable in an academic journal; another helped uncover a 27-year-old vulnerability in a major open-source codebase.
- A recently announced frontier model reportedly identified thousands of zero-day vulnerabilities across critical-infrastructure software; this was repeatedly cited as a step-change rather than gradual progress.
- Practitioners inside frontier AI companies report being shocked at the pace of progress, especially since late 2025; recursive self-improvement of AI capabilities is described as 2 to 3 years away, with internal deployment of the most capable models running ahead of external release, meaning the visible capability gap understates the real one.

- Several technical AI researchers report that AI now writes most of their code; one organisation projects spending more on AI labour than on human labour by year-end.
- Global deployed AI computing capacity is doubling roughly every seven months, a $\sim 10\times$ increase every two years. Capabilities are advancing on a roughly six-month cadence, and many existing scientific benchmarks appear on track to saturate before the end of the decade.
- Annualised recurring revenue at leading frontier AI companies has grown by factors of 10 to 100 over a few years, reaching tens of billions; one cited figure is $>700\%$ revenue growth from one year to the next. This is treated as evidence the trajectory is translating into economic value rather than plateauing.

2.2 The EU is far behind the US and China in frontier AI capabilities, computing infrastructure, and across the wider frontier AI ecosystem. On the current trajectory the gap is widening rather than closing.

- US firms control roughly three-quarters or more of global AI compute, hosted mostly on US soil, while Europe hosts only around 5%. US hyperscalers are on track to build on the order of more than 100 GW by 2028 against a single-digit number of GW in the EU by 2030.
- All planned EU Gigafactories combined are smaller than a single new US data centre that came online this year.
- European frontier models lag behind US and Chinese ones by 6 to 12 months. European AI developers have less than 1% of the revenue of leading American ones; European startups attract about 6% of global AI venture funding.
- US private investment in AI is reported to be on the order of \sim USD 600bn this year, with credible projections of $>$ USD 1tn by 2027; there is no comparable willingness to spend in Europe.
- Multiple European practitioners with direct exposure to leading US AI companies reported, unprompted, that the consensus inside frontier labs is that ‘Europe is cooked’ if it does not act now; the same phrase recurred in the closing summary.

2.3 The main bottlenecks to EU AI competitiveness are access to capital and energy, permitting delays, and specific regulatory obstacles. All of these prevent fast compute buildout. Issues with talent retention and attraction, as well as underperforming demand-side levers, are also part of the picture.

2.3.1 Access to capital, particularly growth and scaling capital

- Frontier AI development is fundamentally capital-intensive, as the scale of investments determines who can build, train, and deploy the most capable models.
- There is a much higher availability of AI growth capital in the US than in Europe; every recent US frontier-lab funding round is in the billions, against which even current European AI champions cannot keep pace.
- Early-stage VC has improved in Europe but scaling capital is still missing; a dedicated multibillion AI growth facility, larger than the UK sovereign AI fund given EU GDP, was repeatedly proposed, alongside mobilising EIB/EIF and pension fund investments.
- Setting up subsidiaries across Member States was described as ‘a fricking pain’; the single market is not single in practice for AI scale-ups, and the path from public to private funding has a structural valley-of-death gap.

2.3.2 Regulatory obstacles to compute and energy buildout; availability and cost of energy

- Computing infrastructure is the substrate of frontier AI: it determines which actors can develop, run, and iterate on the most capable models, and at what speed. Access to large-scale energy and capital investment is the upstream determinant of compute capacity.
- Datacenter and grid-access permitting speed is repeatedly cited as a significant constraint on compute investments; one participant cited rumours that a multi-billion-euro data-centre project in France was reportedly halted over permitting frictions, and claimed that a 2023 EU directive that would have cut renewables permitting had reportedly only been implemented in one Member State by 2025.
- European energy output has been broadly flat for many years, with renewables build-out largely offset by the retirement of nuclear and other conventional capacity; energy prices are correspondingly high. AI was described as a five-layer stack with energy as the foundation.
- Unused legacy grid capacity and brownfield decommissioned coal/lignite sites are flagged as ready substrates for AI-dedicated build-out under streamlined ‘special compute zone’ regimes.

2.3.3 Specific regulatory obstacles to data usage

- Copyright is a frequent obstacle to legally training frontier models in Europe; there is relative clarity in the US; there is significant ambiguity about existing and future requirements in the EU; and ongoing uncertainty risks chilling investment and development. Targeted revisions plus output-based remuneration to rightsholders are repeatedly proposed.
- The current data-protection regime, drafted before the current AI paradigm, is described as preventing legal aggregation of training data at frontier scale; harmonisation and targeted assessments for high-impact sectors are flagged as more urgent than AI-Act-specific reforms.
- Smaller players cannot navigate compliance complexity; help-desk-style support inside agencies, and unified policy frameworks across Member States, are widely supported. Several real-world pilots have reportedly already moved outside Europe to avoid conformity-assessment costs.

2.3.4 Talent retention and attraction

- Some of the researchers and engineers behind the most capable frontier models were trained in Europe yet built their careers in the US or UK, while Europe struggles to offer the salaries, equity, and other conditions needed to attract talent back or recruit globally.
- European-trained researchers behind several recent frontier AI innovations have founded their new companies abroad.
- Inbound migration of AI talent is currently a real opportunity. Talent from outside the EU, including from the US, wants to come, but visa processes take months rather than days. A pan-European, digital, English-language tech visa was repeatedly proposed.
- European salaries cannot currently compete with frontier labs; what works is the package: long-horizon unconditional funding for top individuals, freedom from bureaucracy, infrastructure and compute access, and pan-European institutional homes that bypass Member-State fragmentation.

2.3.5 Demand-side policy and procurement

- Much of the debate focuses on building European frontier AI capacity through supply-side reform, but European AI firms would also benefit from a European market ready to adopt and pay for what they produce.

- The state can act as anchor customer: redirected procurement (one cited example was that a single Member State pays ~EUR 8bn/year to one US software vendor) and procurement vouchers favouring European tech are concrete levers.
- Several speakers warned that public AI factories are at risk of being underused, as bringing a third-party vendor into an enterprise environment is genuinely hard, and the implications of moving workloads away from hyperscalers have not been worked through publicly.

2.4 Frontier AI developments directly affect EU national security and are not just a matter of economic competitiveness

- Frontier AI is already amplifying the threat landscape across multiple domains, lowering the barrier to cyberattacks, enabling the development of biological weapons, and raising novel risks of AI systems pursuing goals misaligned with human intentions. Europe's reliance on non-European frontier models creates a further layer of strategic vulnerability that goes beyond economic competitiveness.
- There is currently no European entity, public or private, that can verify with EU-built tooling and expertise the safety and security claims frontier developers make about their own models.
- One recently announced model's zero-day discovery capability gives both the model provider and the US government a substantial advantage. That capability was shared with a delay of about a month with European governments.
- Wiretapping of EU leaders by allied intelligence services has historical precedent; combined with current capabilities, manipulation of leaders and decision-making is a foreseeable risk.
- While the national security implications of frontier AI appear to be increasingly recognised in countries such as the US and UK, and to prompt the creation of dedicated government bodies and advisor roles, it is unclear to what extent EU Member States' governments prioritise this angle.

2.5 EU sovereignty requires secure access to frontier systems and sufficient inference compute to run such systems at competitive scale

- Some of Europe's fastest-growing AI-application companies largely run on foreign models and foreign cloud infrastructure; access conditions are expected to tighten as models become more capable, and access that depends on someone else's goodwill is not access that can be controlled.
- Even a leading European champion reportedly does its pre-training outside Europe due to lack of compute; without domestic frontier-scale compute on EU soil, every other conversation about sovereignty is described as aspirational.
- Inference compute is its own constraint: deployers want the latest, biggest model, and inference at scale requires bigger and bigger clusters. Owning AI infrastructure is repeatedly framed as a precondition for 'owning anything else' in AI.
- More efficient AI is expected to drive more total AI use, not less compute demand; this means that investing in AI infrastructure today remains a sound bet even if the underlying technology changes.
- Open-weight fine-tuning, auditing and backdoor-scanning capacity on European soil is needed for the scenario where access to frontier closed models is restricted.

2.6 EU AI sovereignty does not require autarky, but leverage and interdependency

- The intuition that Europe should build the whole stack domestically was repeatedly described as a strategic mistake. No country has succeeded at full autarky, and the right route to

sovereignty is having alternatives, not doing everything in-house.

- The Commission and Member States should map interdependencies and identify where Europe has leverage in the supply chain and across the AI stack. They should develop a strategy for if and when to use existing leverage, and how to strengthen and build further leverage.
- Multi-country, multi-cloud and open-source approaches were endorsed for parts of the AI stack; one infrastructure provider noted that researchers in one US state freely use compute from other states and asked why Europe should impose an unreasonably high sovereignty premium on itself instead.
- Resilience comes from sufficient diversity of partners; over-reliance on too few partners is the cautionary lesson, recently exemplified by gas dependencies. Inbound AI talent migration from multiple regions is itself an interdependency advantage.
- Europe’s existing leverage points (e.g. semiconductor lithography, advanced optics, valuable datasets, and the single market) are described as ‘depreciating trump cards’ that need to be activated through coordinated action rather than preserved passively.

2.7 EU institutions and Member States need more internal AI expertise, directly advising the highest political level, and faster, more anticipatory processes that leverage external expertise

- European institutions are described as not prepared for an environment characterised by accelerating frontier AI capabilities and their implications.
- A recurring concrete need is staff with dedicated frontier AI expertise inside government, together with AI advisors at the highest political level, mirroring arrangements in some peer countries.
- The AI Office’s safety unit was described as ‘punching above its weight’ but materially under-resourced relative to even a single private safety research organisation; world-leading capacity is reportedly achievable for less than EUR 100M/year in one organisation.
- AI fast-tracks within institutions to allow experimentation with AI adoption were widely supported.
- Bringing in external experts — including via standing advisory mechanisms modelled on the recent EU AI Act GPAI Code of Practice process, the EU AI Office Scientific Panel, and placements that rotate technical talent through political offices — was repeatedly described as the only practical way to close the expertise gap on a relevant timescale.
- Multiple speakers said this should be among the very top priorities; the gap between political leadership and the technical reality was repeatedly called the biggest obstacle to action.

2.8 European political leaders must prioritise action now, and at a scale not yet contemplated. Without decisive action in the coming months, the European strategic position may become unrecoverable.

- There was broad agreement that European political leaders, including the highest level of the Commission and Member States’ Heads of State and Ministers, must make it a priority to take decisive action in 2026 to strengthen Europe’s position in frontier AI.

The urgency in the room is best conveyed in the speakers’ own words:

“We are not living in normal times; European institutions are not prepared.”

“The consensus in Silicon Valley is that Europe is cooked.” “If Europe doesn’t act now, we’re cooked.” “Every SME in Europe is becoming a ChatGPT wrapper.”

“Unless we have access to the best capabilities, we become politically meaningless.”

“If our AI models [that we have access to] are only 10% worse, this might be an existential threat to EU companies.”

“We need to break the chasm now; after 8 to 10 months it’s too late.” “We need a solution now, not in 10 years.” “2026 must be the year where Europeans turn things around.”

3 Points of partial convergence

Each claim below was supported by multiple speakers across sessions; in each case at least one substantive counter-position was on the record.

3.1 Europe should pursue a ‘middle power’ coalition with allied democracies to pool supply-chain leverage and capabilities development

In favour:

- A coalition with peer middle powers facing the same sovereignty predicament (e.g. no autonomous frontier access) could pool chip procurement, combine existing chokepoints (e.g. lithography, materials, memory) into genuine negotiating weight, and hedge against economic coercion that none could resist alone.
- Concrete proposals included a chip-and-data community making market access conditional, mutual data-protection adequacy to enable compliant cross-border data and compute sharing, and a joint frontier-AI governance initiative with verification mechanisms.
- A summit format bringing the EU together with these middle powers was proposed as the trigger to convert good intentions into a coordinated agenda.

Counterarguments:

- Chokepoint strategies will be unpopular with the chokepoint companies themselves, creating internal political friction.
- Smaller Member States holding key leverage points will be politically afraid to negotiate alone with major powers; the coalition relies on a unified European voice and on a credible mechanism to protect leverage-holders from retaliation, neither of which currently exists.

3.2 Open-source / open-weight models are a strategic asset for European sovereignty, adoption and competition

In favour:

- On the leading model-hosting platform, around 20,000 developers per month contribute fine-tuned derivative models and one open model is released every 1 to 2 minutes; almost half the downloads of popular open models are now in image, video and multimodal domains. Three of the top five open or open-weight models globally were reportedly developed by European founders.
- Open weights enable independent tech stacks, model inspection, modification, fine-tuning and safety assessment — preconditions for genuinely avoiding dependence on remote API providers; they also lower entry barriers for downstream developers and SMEs.
- Substantial public funding is already committed to high-performance open-source European foundation models reflecting linguistic and cultural diversity; open-source labs nonetheless compete on unequal footing and need a tailored regulatory framework.

Counterarguments:

- Most open-weight providers, including European ones, are shifting to a dual strategy: a good open-weight model for branding and an even better closed-weight model that is sold. It is unclear whether genuinely state-of-the-art open-weight models will continue to exist.

- Customers reliably want the most intelligent model available, which raises the risk that, without sustained frontier open weights, open source remains a second tier rather than a sovereignty pillar.

3.3 Europe needs an ARPA-style moonshot funder for AI reliability, safety and security research, in the EUR 100m to 2bn/year range

In favour:

- Reliability research is a structural market failure: at frontier labs, multi-year reliability projects lose to scaling projects with three-month benchmark wins, because being six months behind on capability costs billions while being six months behind on reliability costs nothing today.
- Regulatory demand for ex-ante safety and reliability evidence is already set, but the underlying research pipeline to meet it is unfunded; a comparable UK programme of around £59m has already redirected the agendas of dozens of research groups.
- Estimated funding is roughly EUR 100m/year initially, ramping to ~EUR 2bn/year as compute needs grow.
- Safety-critical industries are over 10% of EU gross value added (versus ~8% in the US), and 48% of European listed corporate champions sit in safety-critical sectors, so reliability research directly unlocks domestic adoption.
- The ARPA model (i.e. empowered programme managers on fixed terms with end-to-end authority, mission-driven portfolios funding competing technical paths in parallel, contracting in weeks not months, and milestone-based cancellation) has 65 years of working comparators, including a recent UK version that pivoted between technical priorities in months while an equivalent EU work programme took over a year to adopt.
- The proposed Franco-German non-profit under the new Frontier AI Initiative is described as a clean institutional slate that could host this without inheriting Horizon-style constraints.

Counterarguments:

- A recurring counter-emphasis was that the binding gap is not research output but the path from a working prototype to an enterprise-operable system: reliability, security hardening, observability and IT integration are chronically underfunded, and many AI initiatives stall at this stage before ever reaching end users. On this framing, the funding instrument should explicitly cover the production layer and not the research phase alone — the same difficulty that puts public AI factories at risk of being underused.
- Some practitioners with direct frontier-lab experience explicitly described ARPA-style and resilience-tech bets as unlikely to deliver on a relevant timescale, and warned against making them the main strategy rather than one portfolio item alongside semiconductor, capital and infrastructure plays.

3.4 Europe needs a verification, evaluation and safety capability, including for cryptographic proofs, audits and assurance, built on European soil

In favour:

- Today's guarantees that model weights cannot be stolen, that access cannot be cut, and that no foreign government can flip a switch are contractual and on paper; with models capable of finding thousands of vulnerabilities, paper guarantees are insufficient and hardware-rooted cryptographic proof is needed.
- A concrete proposal: a task force to identify sites for the first 1 GW of provably-secure data-centre capacity by mid-2027, with every new European data centre from 2028 specifying an independent verification guarantor; the resulting trust layer could be exported globally as

a distinct European product.

- A dedicated technical evaluation institute similar to the UK AISI, complementary to the AI Office and modelled on peer-country safety institutes, was widely supported; world-leading capacity is reportedly achievable at under EUR 100m/year, leveraging existing European centres of excellence rather than founding from scratch.
- Trustworthiness should be reframed as a quality requirement and competitive differentiator rather than a compliance burden. Safety-critical industries (e.g. defence, finance, space, health, critical infrastructure) face a structural obstacle to adopting frontier AI at scale without a recognised certification framework aligned with their regulatory obligations. A dedicated European accreditation pathway for regulated sectors was described as the single structural lever capable of shifting procurement toward European models over non-European alternatives, turning trustworthiness from an adoption barrier into a competitive advantage.

Counterarguments:

- Verification technology is described by some as important but not the main bet; over-investment risks crowding out semiconductor, capital and datacenter plays that more directly determine whether Europe stays in the game.
- Unless safety, fairness and explainability are embedded as optimisation targets during model development rather than bolted on afterwards, the resulting tooling may not deliver the quality dividend it promises.
- A centralised evaluation institute would have to rely on universal, automatically translated datasets and guardrails, which do not work well. An EU Network of AISIs, co-funded by the EU and built upon already existing national initiatives, would be more adequate.

3.5 Physical AI / robotics / world models is the area of strongest convergence as a ‘next wave’ bet for Europe

In favour:

- Europe has an unusually strong industrial substrate for embodied AI: one major manufacturing economy runs the highest density of industrial robots per 10,000 workers in the world, and several existing European companies in this space are already valued in the multi-billions, with full order books.
- Several technical leads on world models and physical-AI breakthroughs are European, and Europe has the industrial data infrastructure (e.g. manufacturing, automotive, pharma, energy) that distinguishes this paradigm from text-only frontier AI; ageing workforces and shortages of skilled physical labour create a genuine pull.
- A concrete proposal modelled on the Airbus consortium was floated: ~EUR 25bn over 10 years, EUR 10bn in EIB/EIF capital plus EUR 15bn in binding offtakes from major European industrial buyers, conditioned on manufacturing the resulting robots in Europe rather than shipping designs abroad as has happened with several recent champions.
- Multiple speakers from very different sectors converged on this as the area where Europe both has substrate and is not yet locked out. This was described as one of the strongest convergence points in the day’s discussion.

Counterarguments:

- Practitioners from leading general-purpose labs warned that generality and scale dominate: their organisations have invested far more in general models than in narrow ones because generality consistently helps.
- The ‘small-and-clever beats big’ narrative was described as ‘Asterix bias’, as AI is overwhelmingly dominated by productively leveraging compute, and a two-order-of-magnitude compute gap cannot be offset by being clever.

3.6 Europe should support frontier-adjacent European companies as ‘fast followers’ even if they are not at the frontier

In favour:

- Building frontier models at scale in the short term is described as unrealistic; supporting European champions to widen the option space, become more competitive over time, and serve as credible domestic alternatives is the practical hybrid strategy.
- Concrete partnerships pairing a European model provider with a major European enterprise-software stack are already in place and were cited as an example of unifying fragmented architectures into a usable European engine for AI use cases.
- Even fast-follower models reduce dependency and preserve the institutional capacity (e.g. through fine-tuning, auditing, and backdoor scanning) needed if access to closed foreign frontier models tightens.
- Sovereignty is not about forcing Europe onto worse models; the value of a domestic fast follower lies mainly in institutional readiness for restricted-access scenarios rather than as a head-to-head replacement.

Counterarguments:

- The leading European frontier-adjacent model is reportedly 6 to 12 months behind, and every recent funding round for the leading foreign labs is in the billions; closing that gap with current European funding scales is widely described as not feasible.
- Even if Europe had the best model, traditional European customers might not buy it: lock-in into hyperscaler stacks is structural, third-party vendor onboarding is complex, and political signalling in some Member States that ‘we cannot do software’ has undermined adoption in the past.

3.7 Europe has a real advantage in private and industrial data

In favour:

- The richest remaining frontier of training data is private and industrial: areas such as manufacturing, healthcare and high-quality national text corpora, where Europe has unusually deep, diverse and well-curated holdings.
- A reference dataset analogous to a single open scientific database has been valued in the tens of billions; the question repeatedly raised was whether Europe can identify and unlock several more such assets, particularly in life sciences.
- What is missing is not the data but the protocols, collective licensing arrangements, rightsholder compensation mechanisms and shared trust infrastructure that would let it be used at scale; existing European data-space initiatives are seen as under-resourced and not yet breaking through.
- A further gap identified was the absence of a shared protocol for letting AI/GPAI systems use one another’s private data under controlled conditions.
- Open, multimodal foundation systems being built across Europe are described as needing connected, synchronised, interoperable datasets rather than larger ones, playing directly to a European strength.

Counterarguments:

- The current data-protection framework, drafted before the present AI paradigm, makes it hard to legally aggregate and process the very data Europe is supposed to have an advantage in; without targeted legal reform the advantage stays locked.
- In practice, sectoral data does not flow: at least one industrial sector reportedly stopped a promising B2B AI project because building the model required handing over too much

intellectual property to the developer.

- Without a European protocol and verification layer to govern and check how data is used, control over the data shifts to whoever runs the processing, rather than staying with its owner.

4 Contested points / unresolved questions

On these questions, multiple speakers defended sharply opposed positions in the same session; the disagreement was not resolved.

4.1 Can Europe ‘leapfrog’ the current paradigm by betting on an alternative one (world models, energy efficiency, distributed AI, quantum) instead of chasing scale?

Pro:

- Current paradigms are reaching their limits (e.g. through diminishing returns, data ceilings, model-collapse risk and severe environmental costs), and Europe is unlikely to win a brute-scale race it has already largely lost; intelligence-per-watt, persistent memory and resource-rational architectures are presented as attractive alternative design objectives.
- A more distributed AI stack, replacing the current centralised supplier stack with many smaller models interacting agentially, would buy resilience and reduce single-vendor dependency, even if total overhead is higher.
- World models, spatial-intelligence and zero-data approaches map directly to European industrial data substrates; one recent paper has shown a simple quantum system outperforming trained language models on a specific task, suggesting a hybridisation route worth at least a portfolio allocation.
- Post-2023 the current AI paradigm was described as a ‘tractor field’ where everyone ploughed the same furrow on language-model scaling; the resulting global gap in fundamental research is precisely the one Europe could plausibly close.

Con:

- Operational metrics like ‘intelligence per watt’ risk crowding out the more relevant metric of ‘value per industrial or public-sector deployment’.
- Practitioners with direct experience inside leading AI companies were unusually blunt: leapfrogging ‘will not work’ on the relevant timescale; nobody at major AI companies believes quantum computing will affect the AI trajectory in the next five years, and the supporting hardware does not exist.
- The ‘small and clever beats big’ framing was repeatedly described as ‘Asterix bias’: AI is overwhelmingly dominated by productively leveraging compute, and a two-order-of-magnitude gap will not be offset by cleverness.
- Even if compute-efficient paradigms emerge, the efficiency will be spent on more AI, not less compute demand; Europe still loses the underlying race.
- Targeting energy-efficient AI before having built systems at the level of current efficiency was described, sharply, as ‘completely delusional’; the operating reality through 2030 is the current paradigm, and the deferral pattern (‘betting on compute, then quantum, then space compute’) is itself a failure mode.

4.2 Should Europe aim to build its own frontier models rather than accept being a fast follower or interdependent partner?

Pro:

- A non-profit frontier effort would need at least EUR 1bn/year for the first few years, frontier-lab-calibre researchers at near-industry compensation, $\geq 100,000$ frontier-class GPUs within months of launch with plans to scale by orders of magnitude, and the freedom to pursue genuine moonshots; the ambition is needed even if success is uncertain.
- To compete in the main paradigm in 2027 Europe would need to invest on the order of USD 1tn/year in compute; foreign companies want to build in Europe and could be permitted to do so. The resulting compute and revenue would be beneficial for European priorities.
- Without domestic frontier-scale investment, Europe risks losing the talent and supply-chain ecosystem needed for any downstream strategy, including fast-follower work; on this view ambition comes first, not last.

Con:

- Building frontier models from Europe in the short term is described as not realistic given the scale of foreign private investment, the missing capital, and the missing compute and talent; a hybrid strategy of strategic partnerships with foreign frontier labs, backed by hard leverage from chokepoints and the single market, is presented as the only viable near-term path.
- The objective should be sovereignty, not outbuilding others: backing a small number of public-private frontier-adjacent efforts to preserve optionality, while expanding evaluation and verification capacity, achieves more for less.
- Even within the more ambitious framing, several speakers explicitly said Europe should not bet its future on building its own base models; the more durable bet is securing access to foreign frontier systems through pooled supply-chain leverage.

4.3 Should general-purpose / scaled models or narrow / domain-specific AI be Europe's primary bet?

Pro 'narrow / domain-specific':

- Purpose-driven systems built on high-quality domain data (e.g. protein structure, weather, scientific simulation, industrial control) have repeatedly outperformed general-purpose models in their own domains and represent areas where Europe already has the data and the domain expertise.
- Europe has a substantial B2B opportunity in highly reliable industrial models that large incumbents will fund and embed; this fits European industrial structure better than consumer chatbot markets.
- Distillation of large open-source models into smaller, task-specific systems is a credible European specialisation; vertical optimisation per sector (e.g. pharma, automotive, manufacturing) mirrors a strategy already pursued elsewhere with success.
- Smaller, locally runnable models also fit European preferences for efficiency and on-device deployment, and reduce dependence on hyperscaler inference.

Pro 'general-purpose / scaled':

- Leading AI companies have consistently invested far more in general models than in narrow ones because generality compounds: broad datasets and broad capabilities transfer across tasks in ways narrow systems do not, and ignoring that benefit was described as a massive failure mode.
- Customers reliably want the most intelligent model available; the European narrative of frugal, specialised, efficient systems repeatedly loses out in actual deployment to whichever model is most capable, even when that model is overkill on paper.
- Recent and projected automation of most non-physical work is being driven by broad, general capability; a strategy built mainly around the narrow case may understate the disruption Europe faces.

- ‘Leading in narrow AI’ while ignoring what general-purpose foreign systems are doing was described as a failure mode; Europe should take the dominant paradigm seriously and play to strengths within it, not around it.

4.4 Is the framing of AI as primarily a danger (versus an opportunity) itself a strategic liability for Europe?

Pro:

- Europe is described as having ‘taught a whole continent that AI is a danger, not a chance’; the dominant regulatory framing communicates risk as the headline, and small businesses cannot tell whether they are compliant — they can only tell that engaging is risky.
- Many people in European policy and business circles still do not see the value of the technology and instead hope for a new architecture to appear; that perception itself depresses adoption, founder ambition and capital flow, on top of any specific regulatory cost.
- Founders cite capital and single-market frictions as reasons new companies are incorporated abroad, and the ‘danger’ framing is described as compounding these; on this view the frame is not a neutral description but a competitive handicap.
- A reframing toward opportunity in every European strategic initiative was repeatedly proposed, with concrete asks that European industrial champions and governments be visible early adopters of European AI to shift the cultural signal.

Con:

- The European regulatory tradition is widely seen abroad as a template; harmonising and explaining it better is presented as more urgent than reframing it. Several speakers explicitly described the AI Act as something to be proud of.
- Trustworthiness, reliability, fairness and explainability can be operationalised as quality requirements and optimisation targets rather than as compliance burdens — a third framing that neither the ‘danger’ nor the ‘opportunity’ rhetoric captures.
- Values-based positioning is itself a talent-attraction lever: prospective researchers cite mission alignment, and credible European commitments to safety and rights could support inbound migration.
- Bot-driven adoption and engagement metrics reportedly inflate foreign demand signals; Europe’s commitment to integrity is a real differentiator that should not be discarded in the rush to a ‘pro-innovation’ framing.

4.5 Is the dominant US AI investment trajectory a sustainable trend or a bubble Europe should not chase?

Pro ‘real, sustainable’:

- Annualised recurring revenue at frontier labs is in the tens of billions and growing more than fivefold per year; deployed compute capacity is doubling every seven months, and capability progress on objective benchmarks tracks compute investment closely. The economic value is showing up in the numbers, not just in marketing.
- AI is in reach of automating most non-physical work on the current trajectory; even substantial discounts on the most aggressive forecasts still leave a transformation that Europe cannot afford to sit out.
- The narrative that foreign AI investment is a bubble Europe can leapfrog around (e.g. through energy efficiency, quantum, or new architectures) was described by practitioners with direct lab experience as straightforwardly wrong; Europe needs domestic compute and to strengthen its position within the dominant paradigm, not bet against it.

Pro ‘partly bubble / read with caution’:

- Demand at the high end is described by some as partly manufactured: heavily subsidised consumer offerings, including reportedly loss-making premium tiers at major labs, inflate apparent willingness to pay and user growth.
- If the technology plateaus and the most aggressive promises (e.g. recursive self-improvement, omnipotent AI within a few years) are not met, much of the strategy currently being designed against those promises will look misallocated; a more diversified bet (including smaller models, domain-specific systems, and applications consumers actually want rather than chatbots) would be more robust.
- Cracks are visible in the foreign trajectory itself: AI talent migration into the leading market has reportedly dropped sharply, public sentiment is turning bipartisan-negative, and pushback against data centres is growing; Europe should read these signals when calibrating how much to chase.

Endorsers

The following forum participants confirm that the elements made public in this document broadly represent what they heard in the sessions that they attended. They do not endorse any particular views. Listed in alphabetical order:

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